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FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

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E-RIHS National Node Info Survey

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Text version of the survey. It is for your information only. Fill out the web version, please.

E-RIHS-IP_NN_survey

The current state of National Nodes – a survey.

This survey has been prepared under the Interim Committee of National Nodes decision of October 12, 2022 as a part of the preparation for the implementation of the E-RIHS IP project and the establishment of the E-RIHS ERIC. The purpose is to gather up-to-date information of the state of preparation of National Nodes (already established and in the process of establishing) for participation in the E-RIHS ERIC. The results will be presented during the workshop organised by E-RIHS IP in June 2023.

To make your response most comparable with others refer, please, to the following **definitions**:

- **In-kind contribution**: A contribution in terms of person/time, infrastructure depreciation costs, material costs or other costs, that can be evaluated financially: (i) to access projects in the frame of E-RIHS ERIC, or (ii) to the operations of the E-RIHS ERIC or E-RIHS ERIC Governance.
- **Access fee**: A financial contribution by the external user for approved access either through: (i) E-RIHS ERIC Central Office, or (ii) E-RIHS National Node.
- **E-RIHS ERIC Membership fee**: A financial contribution by the E-RIHS ERIC Member country to E-RIHS ERIC.
- **E-RIHS National Node partner fee**: A financial contribution by the partner institution of an E-RIHS National Node. *This could either be an E-RIHS National Node-related cash contribution to the lead institution/ ad hoc legal entity, a regular budget in a partner institution earmarked for E-RIHS National Nodes activities, or an exceptional cash contribution dedicated to national E-RIHS activity.*
- **National Own contribution**: A contribution in terms of person/time, infrastructure purchase or depreciation costs, material costs or other costs, that can be evaluated financially: (i) to access projects in the frame of E-RIHS National Node, or (ii) to the operations of the E-RIHS National Node (or its representatives in E-RIHS ERIC). Own contribution is normally allocated from institutional budgets.
- **National E-RIHS grant**: A grant by the national (or regional) funding agency specifically to cover the cost of operation of the E-RIHS National Node (or equivalent). Such grants could cover the costs of access, travel, consumables, organisational and administrative costs etc. at the national level. *This terminology could also apply to grants given by the National Node to the partners to perform their duties (like in the Netherlands).*
- **National E-RIHS infrastructure investment**: A grant or award by the national (or regional) funding agency or other funders, specifically to cover the cost of investment into physical or digital research infrastructure for the purpose of E-RIHS, either nationally or internationally.

- Ad hoc legal entity: a company, an association or another type of organization that has legal rights and responsibilities, including the right to make contracts (*for example, Service Level Agreements*), to pay E-RIHS ERIC membership fees, and the responsibility to pay debts, established for the purpose of participating in E-RIHS ERIC.
- Legally binding consortium agreement: a contract between partners that is enforceable under national (and thus European) Law. National Nodes using these options cannot formally have legal personality. This option gives more flexibility in terms of commitment.
- Legal personality is the ability to sign legal documents as the Node, either through an ad hoc legal entity or with a mandate from all partners
- Services refer to procedures/techniques/methods/archives, analogous to the items listed in the IPERION HS Transnational Access offer: MOLAB-like: service provided at User's location, FIXLAB-like: service provided at Provider's facility (laboratory), ARCHLAB-like: access to the Providers' archives
- Access project: a single project, with a defined beneficiary, may comprise one or more services
- Unit of access: a common measure of involvement of the provider into a service, usually counted in units of time (days, hours etc.)
- Full-time equivalent (counted in personal months – PM): to calculate, divide the total amount (as for p. 18a) by 12 x the average monthly full-time salary of the person employed in a similar position
- DIGILAB: digital knowledge and data repositories, collaborative tools, and online research facilities exploitable by the Heritage Science community. National DIGILAB refers to such resources directly organised or co-organised by your National Node.

(Mandatory fields shown in blue)

Section 1: General Information

1. Please tell us who is responding to this survey:
 - a) Country of the National Node you are responding on behalf of:
 - b) Name:
 - c) Surname:
 - d) e-mail:
 - e) Role in the National Node:

2. Has the National Node already been formed in your country?

Note: for the purpose of this survey, the National Node (NN) is an organisation, organised structure, or informal network composed of a defined group of entities with an agreed lead (or at least a leading person) or a single legal entity.

• **YES**

List below all entities involved (provide names in the national language/in English), if your National Node has got a lead institution, list it at first:

1. Institution: /

Is this institution considered to be the lead institution?

- YES**
- NO**

Add next institution?

- YES**

Other institutions of your Node, one per line: national language / English:

.....
.....

• **NO**

Explain why and clarify any future plans:

Note: because you have answered NO, try to answer the following questions in respect to any HS related activities in your country either in your institution or other organisation

3. Is the National Node has (or it is planned to have) a tiered membership structure

• **YES**

please clarify:

• **NO**

• **NOT APPLICABLE** (choose this option only if the National Node has not been formed yet)

4. What number of entities form your National Node?

Note: if the Node has not been formed yet, estimate, please, enter the number of entities potentially forming such a structure

- a. Public academic institutions (e.g. universities)
- b. Public research institutes (e.g. of academy of science)

- c. Public conservation/restoration entities
- d. Industrial research institutes
- e. Public museums, galleries, libraries, archives or other heritage/archaeological institutions ...
- f. Other public entities not listed above
- g. Other private entities not listed above

5. Is your National Node, your national E-RIHS structure or E-RIHS (as ESFRI project), included in the National Roadmap of Research Infrastructures?

- **YES**
Since when (year only):
- **NO**
- **NO National Road Map has been established in my country**

6. Does your National Node have a dedicated website?

- **YES**
Please provide the URL:
- **NO**

6. Other comments to Section 1:

Section 2: Structure of the National Node

8. Is your National Node established under a formal legal agreement?

- Single institution/organisation, an ad hoc legal entity (i.e., established for the purpose), a single institution or organisation with a formal and full mandate from partners, to represent the National Node
Note: *ad hoc legal entity means a company, an association or another type of organization that has legal rights and responsibilities, including the right to make contracts (for example, Service Level Agreements), to pay E-RIHS ERIC membership fees, and the responsibility to pay debts, established for the purpose of participating in E-RIHS ERIC.*
- A legally binding agreement with provisions that cover the commitment of all institutions or organisations to the ERIC. Name the structure and the type of legal agreement:
Note: *A "legally binding consortium agreement" or any other kind of binding agreement like a Joint Research Unit is a contract between partners that is enforceable under national (and thus European)*

Law. National Nodes using these options cannot formally have legal personality. This option gives more flexibility in terms of commitment.

Chose one, please:

- Consortium agreement
- Joint Research Unit
- Memorandum of Understanding
- Association agreement
- Other types of agreement name.

Clarify, please:

- A non-binding agreement

Clarify, please:

- **NOT APPLICABLE** (choose this option only if the National Node has not been formed yet)

9. Does your National Node have a legal personality?

***Note:** Legal personality is the ability to sign legal documents as the Node, either through an ad hoc legal entity or with a mandate from all partners*

- **YES**
- **NO**

Clarify who the signatory is and how the signing process is handled (e.g. all members sign, or a lead institution can sign on behalf of National Node partners)

- **NOT APPLICABLE** (choose this option only if the National Node has not been formed yet)

10. Other comments to Section 2:

Section 3: Access

11. Does your National Node (or equivalent structure) provide access to facilities (independently to IPERION HS)?

- **YES**

a) Is such access awarded through a competitive process?

- YES**
- NO**

- b) Are the rules for access provision (including the selection process) formalised in a public document?
- YES**
Provide a link, if available or explain if not, please
 - NO**
- c) Is there personnel formally dedicated to access management? (Either through direct employment, secondment, or other formal commitments)
- YES**
 - NO**
- d) Is there funding formally dedicated to access costs (including operation costs, travel and accommodation for users or MOLAB researchers)?
- YES**
 - NO**
- e) Does a user pay an access fee (see *Definitions*)?
- YES**
 - NO**
- f) How many types of services is your National Node offering in 2023:
- Note:** services refer to procedures/techniques/methods/archives, analogous to the items listed in the IPERION HS Transnational Access offer: MOLAB-like: service provided at User's location, FIXLAB-like: service provided at Provider's facility (laboratory), ARCHLAB-like: access to the Providers' archives
- i. MOLAB-like service(s)
 - ii. FIXLAB-like service(s)
 - iii. ARCHLAB-like service(s)
- g) How many access projects, not counting IPERION HS access, were completed in 2021: access project(s) ;
- Note:** Access project: a single project, with a defined beneficiary, may comprise one or more services
- h) How many access projects, not counting IPERION HS access, were completed in 2022: access project(s).
- i) What types of institutions are your users typically associated with/employed at? Please provide an approximate distribution (in %):
- i. Public sector (e.g., museums, libraries and other public institutions, NGOs) ... %
 - ii. Private sector %
 - iii. Research/academic %
 - iv. Other (e.g., religious organisations) %

j) Can you identify and calculate units of access related to the services offered?

Note: *unit of access is a common measure of involvement of the provider into a service, usually counted in units of time (days, hours etc.)*

YES

Name it, please:

NO

k) Do you use units of access as a common practice in your Node (e.g., cost model of access)

YES

NO

l) Do you know how to/can you calculate the monetary cost of the access services offered?

YES

Partially (for some institutions only)

NO

m) Is there a cost model for the access services offered?

YES

Partially (for some institutions only)

NO

• **NO**

Do you plan to start providing access to facilities (separately to IPERION HS)?

YES

NO

Clarify, please:

12. What activities supporting the heritage science community does your National Node provide/participate in (multiple options possible)?

- Training
- Conferences
- Summer schools
- Project preparation and implementation
- Policy
- Joint Research Activities
- Public engagement
- Grant funding
- Other expert support
- Other,

Clarify “other”, please:

13. Other comments to Section 3:

Section 4: Budget

14. Estimate the average annual budget of your National Node, in Euro (including both monetary and in-kind contributions for access, training and any other activities supporting the HS community)?

Note: do not include IPERION HS and ERIHS IP funding. Leave the field empty if an estimation is not possible.

Monetary:

In-kind:

15. Is your National Node currently directly funded?

Note: do not include IPERION HS and ERIHS IP funding, only dedicated and specific funding for National Node activities. Do not include in-kind contribution from partner institutions.

• **YES**

15a. What is the monetary income structure of your National Node (including access, infrastructure upgrade and maintenance, training and any other HS activities linked to E-RIHS) in Euro, in 2022:

- Financial contributions from member/partner institutions:
- European Structural Investment Funds ...
- National funding (from national funding agencies/ministries/analogous institutions and organisations)
- Regional funding (from regional funding agencies/analogous institutions and organisations)
- Access fees from public bodies/organizations
- Access fees from private organizations
- Private donations or grants (e.g., foundations, charities)
- European Commission grants

15b. If your National Node has received European Commission grants such as Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe (excluding IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP funding, also any funding granted directly to Node members) for E-RIHS-related activities or services, please indicate which ones (multiple choice possible):

- Joint Research activities for improving services or developing new ones

- Training
- Research projects that make use of E-RIHS facilities
- Public engagement
- Recommendations for policy-making or standardisation
- Networking and synergies with other European initiatives
- Other
- NON-APPLICABLE (choose this option only if the National Node has not been beneficiary of EC grants)

15c. Do you have a 5-year budget plan?

- YES**
- No**

15d. Do you have shared accounting practices or guidelines?

- YES**

Note: "established standard cost" refers to an agreed list of costs, typically publicly available.

- Based on actual costs
- Based on a fair market value approach
- Based on established standard costs

- NO**

- We plan to adopt common rules for cost estimation
- We do not plan to adopt common rules for cost estimation
- It depends on future ERIC requirements

16. Do you anticipate your National Node to receive funding in 2024?

- YES**
- NO**
- DON'T KNOW**

17. Is your National Node subjected to mandatory reporting (e.g., related to the National Roadmap updating) or national audits?

- YES**
- Partially**
- NO**

18. What is the annual cost structure of the National Node (in Euro)?

- 18a. Employed personnel (cost of staff, including only personnel employed specifically for National Node services) by amount: EURO.
- 18b. Employed personnel (cost of staff, including only personnel employed specifically for National Node services) by full-time equivalent: PM
Note: *Full-time equivalent (counted in personal months – PM): to calculate, divide the total amount (as for p. 18a) by 12 x the average monthly full-time salary of the person employed in a similar position*
- 18c. In-Kind Human Resources (cost of staff, including personnel employed at partner institutions and providing services instead of monetary contributions) by amount EURO
- 18d. In-Kind Human Resources (cost of staff, including personnel employed at partner institutions and providing services in lieu of monetary contributions) by full time equivalent: PM
- 18e. Consumables, training, travel and other costs EURO
- 18f. Investments into infrastructure and equipment, including servicing EURO

19. Do you have a separate service and maintenance budget?

- YES
- NO

20. Provide an estimate of funding for future infrastructure/instrumentation upgrades in the 5-year perspective? (Please enter the estimated numerical value in €)

Public funding EURO

Private funding/donors EURO

21. Do you have a 5-year infrastructure/instrumentation upgrade plan?

- YES
- NO

22. Other comments to Section 4:

Section 5: Future plans

23. Please provide a rough and not binding estimation of the number of services the National Node will propose for inclusion in the Catalogue of Services of ERIHS ERIC:

Note: services refer to procedures/techniques/methods/archives, analogous to the items listed in the IPERION HS Transnational Access offer: MOLAB-like: service provided at User's location, FIXLAB-like: service provided at Provider's facility (laboratory), ARCHLAB-like: access to the Providers' archives (enter zeros if the National Node has not been formed yet)

- a) ARCHLAB: services
- b) FIXLAB: services
- c) MOLAB: services

24. Are you planning or already offering access to a National DIGILAB?

Note: DIGILAB refers to "digital knowledge and data repositories, collaborative tools, and online research facilities" exploitable by the Heritage Science community. National DIGILAB refers to such resources directly organised or co-organised by your National Node.

- YES
Clarify, please:
- NO

25. Are you following established rules (referring to FAIR principles, open Data) for the Data produced in Access projects, as part of a Data Management Policies / Data repositories framework at **National level**?

- YES
- NO
- DON'T KNOW

26. Has your country already committed or has plans to commit to participation in the E-RIHS ERIC?

- YES

- **NO**

Are the scientific or professional representatives of your country willing to join the Enlargement Board?

Note: the Enlargement Board (EB) is made up of scientists representing Countries that are either not yet engaged in E-RIHS or are engaged in E-RIHS, without supporting the establishment of the ERIC yet. The EB will be engaged during the project ERIHS-IP lifetime to boost interest in E-RIHS, and it will be provided with information and documents necessary to start the national process to join E-RIHS ERIC.

- YES**

Please provide the contact e-mails:

- NO**

27. Other comments to Section 5:

28. Other comments the survey as a whole:

Thank you for your time!

Piotr Targowski

With contributions from:

Brenda Doherty, Rémi Petitcol, Polona Ropret, Sophia Sotiropoulou, Matija Strlič, Jan van t'Hof, Vania Virgili

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
Implementation Phase

Grant Agreement No. 101079148

WP2 GOVERNANCE AND STRUCTURE OF E-RIHS

Task 2.2: Supporting the establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes

National Node Survey

Survey prepared by: Piotr Targowski, Brenda Doherty, Jan van t'Hof, Rémi Petitcol, Polona Ropret, Matija Strlič, Vania Virgili, Sophia Sotiropoulou

Data provided by National Nodes Coordinators: Demetrios Anglos, António Candeias, Emilio Cano, JoAnn Cassar, May Cassar, Matthew Collins, Lavinia de Ferri, Wim Fremout, Sorin Hermon, Costanza Miliani, Sara Norrehed, Rémi Petitcol, Roxana Rădvan, Matija Strlič, Polonca Ropret, Zita Szikszai, Piotr Targowski, Jan van 't Hof

Results evaluated by: Piotr Targowski, Magdalena Kowalska

This survey has been prepared under the Interim Committee of National Nodes decision of October 12, 2022 as a part of the preparation for the implementation of the E-RIHS IP project and the establishment of the E-RIHS ERIC. The purpose is to gather up-to-date information of the state of preparation of National Nodes (already established and in the process of establishing) for participation in the E-RIHS ERIC. The results will be presented during the workshop organised by E-RIHS IP in June 2023.

It was prepared with (https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey).

EUSurvey is a web application for online survey creation and publication developed and maintained by DG DIGIT, the Directorate-General for Informatics of the European Commission. EUSurvey is supported by the European Commission's DEP-Interoperability programme, which promotes interoperability solutions for European public administrations

The numbers below are rough estimates and express solely the opinion of the person who filled the questionnaire. Data filled is to be used only internally within the E-RIHS IP project as indicative and not for any scientific purpose, policy advise, deliverable or any other publication, without prior formal consent by its author.

Table of content

Definitions	5
Section 1: General Information	6
1. Who is responding to this survey:	6
2. Has the National Node already been formed in your country?	7
3. Is the National Node has (or it is planned to have) a tiered membership structure	9
4. What kind of entities form your National Node?	9
5. Is your National Node, your national E-RIHS structure or E-RIHS (as ESFRI project), included in the National Roadmap of Research Infrastructures?	11
6. Does your National Node have a dedicated website?.....	12
7. Other comments to Section 1.....	13
Section 2: Structure of the National Node	14
8. Is your National Node established under a formal legal agreement?.....	14
9. Does your National Node have a legal personality?.....	15
10. Other comments to Section 2:	16
Section 3: Access	17
11. Does your National Node (or equivalent structure) provide access to facilities (independently to IPERION HS)?	17
12. What activities supporting the heritage science community does your National Node provide/participate in (multiple options possible)?	22

13. Other comments to Section 3:	24
Section 4: Budget	26
14. Estimate the average annual budget of your National Node, in Euro.....	26
15. Is your National Node currently directly funded?	27
15b. If your National Node has received European Commission grants such as Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe (excluding IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP funding, also any funding granted directly to Node members) for E-RIHS-related activities or services, please indicate which ones :	28
15c. Do you have a 5-year budget plan?.....	29
15d. Do you have shared accounting practices or guidelines?	30
16. Do you anticipate your National Node to receive funding in 2024?	30
17. Is your National Node subjected to mandatory reporting (e.g., related to the National Roadmap updating) or national audits?.....	31
18. What is the annual cost structure of the National Node (in Euro)?.....	32
19. Do you have a separate service and maintenance budget?.....	33
20. Provide an estimate of funding for future infrastructure/instrumentation upgrades in the 5-year perspective? (Please enter the estimated numerical value in €).....	34
21. Do you have a 5-year infrastructure/instrumentation upgrade plan?.....	34
22. Other comments to Section 4:	35
Section 5: Future plans.....	37
23. Please provide a rough and not binding estimation of the number of services the National Node will propose for inclusion in the Catalogue of Services of ERIHS ERIC:.....	37
24. Are you planning or already offering access to a National DIGILAB?.....	38
25. Are you following established rules (referring to FAIR principles, open Data) for the Data produced in Access projects, as part of a Data Management Policies / Data repositories framework at National level?	39
26. Has your country already committed or has plans to commit to participation in the E-RIHS ERIC?.....	39
27. Are the scientific or professional representatives of your country willing to join the Enlargement Board?	40
28. Other comments to Section 5:	40
29. Other comments the survey as a whole:.....	41
Appendix 1: Complete list of institutions forming a National Node (if established)	43

Notice: Every section ends with “Other comments”. If the comment is specific for the given question it is also repeated directly after this question.

Definitions

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- E-RIHS National Node partner fee: A financial contribution by the partner institution of an E-RIHS National Node. *This could either be an E-RIHS National Node-related cash contribution to the lead institution/ ad hoc legal entity, a regular budget in a partner institution earmarked for E-RIHS National Nodes activities, or an exceptional cash contribution dedicated to national E-RIHS activity.*
- National Own contribution: A contribution in terms of person/time, infrastructure purchase or depreciation costs, material costs or other costs, that can be evaluated financially: (i) to access projects in the frame of E-RIHS National Node, or (ii) to the operations of the E-RIHS National Node (or its representatives in E-RIHS ERIC). Own contribution is normally allocated from institutional budgets.
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- **DIGILAB**: digital knowledge and data repositories, collaborative tools, and online research facilities exploitable by the Heritage Science community. National DIGILAB refers to such resources directly organised or co-organised by your National Node.

Section 1: General Information

1. Who is responding to this survey:

A: National Node Committee members; **B:** National Node Candidates

Country of the National Node	Your name:	Your surname:	Your e-mail	Role in the National Node:
Belgium	Wim	Fremout	wim.fremout@kikirpa.be	national coordinator
Cyprus	sorin	hermon	s.hermon@cyi.ac.cy	planning
France	Rémi	Petitcol	e-rihs.fr@sciences-patrimoine.org	Host institution employee
Greece	Demetrios	Anglos	anglos@iesl.forth.gr	coordinator
Hungary	Zita	Szikszai	szikszai.zita@atomki.hu	national coordinator
Italy	Costanza	Miliani	costanza.miliani@cnr.it	Coordinator
Malta	JoAnn	Cassar	joann.cassar@um.edu.mt	Coordinator
Netherlands	Jan	van 't Hof	j.van.t.hof@cultureelerfgoed.nl	National Coordinator
Poland	Piotr	Targowski	ptarg@UMK.pl	Coordinator
Portugal	António	Candeias	candeias@uevora.pt	coordinator
Romania	Roxana	Rădvan	radvan@inoe.ro	Coordinator
Slovenia	Matija and Polonca	Strlič and Ropret	polona.ropret@zvks.si	Chair of the Management Board and National Coordinator
Spain	Emilio	Cano	ecano@cenim.csic.es	Coordinator
UK	May	Cassar	m.cassar@ucl.ac.uk	Interim National Co-ordinator
B				
Denmark	Matthew	Collins	matthew@palaeome.org	Coordinator
Norway	Lavinia	de Ferri	l.de.ferri@khm.uio.no	coordinator
Sweden	Sara	Norrehed	sara.norrehed@raa.se	coordinator

Invitations have been sent also to the following countries: Austria, Brazil, Czech Republic, Germany, Israel, Mexico, US-East, US-West

2. Has the National Node already been formed in your country?

Country of the National Node	member of iGA?	Has the National Node already been formed in your country?	Formal access to ERIC – STEP 2?*	Institution 1 (lead) - national language / English	Explanation for NO
Belgium	YES	YES		Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium / Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	
Cyprus	NO	NO	YES		Will establish the node after the country committed to support the E-RIHS ERIC.
France	YES	YES		Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine - Foundation for Heritage Science	
Greece	YES	YES		ITE / FORTH	
Hungary	YES	YES	YES	Atommagkutató Intézet / Institute for Nuclear Research (Debrecen)	
Italy	YES	YES	YES	National Research Council	
Malta	YES	YES	YES	Universita' ta' Malta/University of Malta	
Netherlands	YES	NO	YES		The node is at the moment a network and we will look into a more formal status in 2023-2024
Poland	YES	YES		Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika w Toruniu / Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń	
Portugal	YES	YES		Laboratório HERCULES - Universidade de Évora / HERCULES Laboratory - Evora University	
Romania	YES	YES		The National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics INOE 2000	

Slovenia	YES	YES	YES	Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine Slovenije / Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia	
Spain	YES	YES	YES	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas / Spanish National Research Council	
UK	YES	YES		UCL	
Total A	13/1	12/2	7		
B					
Denmark	NO	YES		The University of Copenhagen	
Norway	NO	NO			The Project was submitted in the frame of the INFRA2020 calls for infrastructures of the Norwegian Research Council. SciCult placed first on the waiting list of unfunded projects and we are still waiting to be contacted by NFR. However, NFR had major financial problems last year and the time frame for the distribution of funds has lengthened significantly. In any case, we have just received communication of the opening of the new INFRA2023 call and we are preparing to apply in case NRF is unable to confirm us.
Sweden	NO	NO			Received rejection to national infrastructure applications.
Total B	0/3	1/2			
Total A+B	13/4	13/4			

*Formal letter sent to iGA, as of May 19, 2023

Complete list of institutions forming a National Node (if established) in given in Appendix 1.

Sweden: Heritage Science Sweden exists as a network.

Norway: The list of partners currently includes a total of 7 institutions of which 2 are different (at the administrative level) headquarters of the same university. Additionally, in view of the new submission we are evaluating the possibility to involve 2 more universities and a total of 9 museums. However only one of them

has the state of research institute, essential to be included as a partner in the NRC application. If none of the others will get this status, they may be listed as associated partners or stakeholders depending on the possibilities.

3. Is the National Node has (or it is planned to have) a tiered membership structure

Country of the National Node	3. Is the National Node has (or it is planned to have) a tiered membership structure?	Clarify, please:
Belgium	NOT	
Cyprus	NOT APPLICABLE	
France	YES	Parent authorities are members of the governing board. Research units can join the node's General Assembly of Access providers with a simple validation of their main parent authorities. Other institutions act as scientific partners on specific topics through MoUs or through the FSP.
Greece	NOT	
Hungary	NOT	
Italy	YES	Joint Research Unit
Malta	NOT	
Netherlands	NOT APPLICABLE	
Poland	NOT	
Portugal	NOT	
Romania	YES	The National Node (HUB) has three national institutes, and collaborates with a national network that includes:
Slovenia	NOT	
Spain	NOT	
UK	NOT	
B		
Denmark	NOT	
Norway	NOT APPLICABLE	
Sweden	NOT APPLICABLE	

4. What kind of entities form your National Node?

Note: if the Node has not been formed yet, estimate, please, enter the number of entities potentially forming such a structure

Country of the National Node	Public academic institutions (e.g. universities)	Public research institutes (e.g. of academy of science)	Public conservation/restoration entities	Industrial research institutes	Public museums, galleries, libraries, archives or other heritage/archaeological institutions	Other public entities not listed above	Other private entities not listed above	Total
Belgium	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	3
Cyprus	3	1	0	0	3	1	1	9
France	7	1	3	0	0	0	0	11
Greece	0	5	0	0	0	0	1	6
Hungary	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	4
Italy	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
Malta	1	0	2	0	5	2	0	10
Netherlands	4	4	1	0	1	1	1	12
Poland	8	4	0	0	1	0	0	13
Portugal	1	1	1	0	26	0	0	29
Romania	2	4	1	0	1	0	0	8
Slovenia	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	8
Spain	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	8
UK	10	2	0	0	8	0	0	20
Total A	42	35	11	0	49	4	3	144
B								
Denmark	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	4
Norway	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	6
Sweden	3	0	0	1	4	0	0	8
Total B	10	0	2	1	5	0	0	18
Total A+B	52	35	13	1	54	4	3	162

France: only parent authorities are counted as entities, but a few providers have their own legal personality

Italy: Italian node is pursuing an enlargement policy towards those Universities already engaged with E-RIHS through previous INFRAIA EU-funded and national projects, e.g. the University of Bologna, University of Florence, University of Naples.

Malta: Some of the entities involved have a dual function e.g. museum or archive and conservation/restoration facilities

5. Is your National Node, your national E-RIHS structure or E-RIHS (as ESFRI project), included in the National Roadmap of Research Infrastructures?

Country of the National Node	5. Is your National Node, your national E-RIHS structure or E-RIHS (as ESFRI project) included in the National Roadmap of Research Infrastructures?	Since when (year only):
Belgium	NO National Road Map has been established in my country	
Cyprus	NO National Road Map has been established in my country	
France	YES	2016
Greece	YES	2014
Hungary	YES	2018
Italy	YES	2013
Malta	NO National Road Map has been established in my country	
Netherlands	YES	2021
Poland	YES	2020
Portugal	YES	2016

Romania	YES	2017
Slovenia	YES	2016
Spain	NO National Road Map has been established in my country	
Sweden	NO	
UK	YES	2015
Total A	10/0/4 No RM	
B		
Denmark	YES	2022
Norway	NO	
Sweden	NO	
Total B	1/2	
Total A+B	11/2/4 No RM	

Hungary: The National Road Map acknowledges the initiatives but it does not linked to direct financial support for them. However, being on the Road Map might give extra points at various calls.

6. Does your National Node have a dedicated website?

Country of the National Node you are responding on behalf of:	Does your National Node have a dedicated website?	Please provide the URL:
Belgium	NO	
Cyprus	NO	
France	YES	www.erihs.fr
Greece	YES	www.e-rihs.gr
Hungary	YES	e-rihs.hu
Italy	YES	www.e-rihs.it
Malta	YES	www.e-rihs.mt
Netherlands	YES	e-rihs.nl
Poland	YES	www.e-rihs.pl
Portugal	YES	www.e-rihs.pt
Romania	YES	e-rihs.ro
Slovenia	YES	www.e-rihs.si
Spain	YES	www.e-rihs.es
UK		
B		
Denmark	YES	e-rihs.dk
Norway	NO	
Sweden	YES	heritagescience.se

Comments:

France: Our website is currently outdated due to technical difficulties with the local server. A relaunch and update are foreseen this year.

Malta: The website still under construction and is being updated to E-RIHS format

7. Other comments to Section 1

Country of the National Node:	Other comments to Section 1:
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our website is currently outdated due to technical difficulties with the local server. A relaunch and update are foreseen this year. • Question 4: only parent authorities are counted as entities, but a few providers have their own legal personality
Greece	
Hungary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Road Map acknowledges the initiatives but it does not linked to direct financial support for them. However, being on the Road Map might give extra points at various calls.
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italian node is pursuing an enlargement policy towards those Universities already engaged with E-RIHS through previous INFRAIA EU-funded and national projects, e.g. the University of Bologna, University of Florence, University of Naples.
Malta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the entities involved have a dual function e.g. museum or archive and conservation/restoration facilities • The website still under construction and is being updated to E-RIHS format
Netherlands	
Poland	
Portugal	
Romania	
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No comment.
Spain	
UK	
B	
Denmark	
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The list of partners currently includes a total of 7 institutions of which 2 are different (at the administrative level) headquarters of the same university. Additionally, in view of the new submission we are evaluating the possibility to involve 2 more universities and a total of 9 museums. However only one of them has the state of research institute, essential to be included as a partner in the NRC application. If none of the others will get this status, they may be listed as associated partners or stakeholders depending on the possibilities.
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heritage Science Sweden exists as a network.

Section 2: Structure of the National Node

8. Is your National Node established under a formal legal agreement?

- Single institution/organisation, an ad hoc legal entity (i.e., established for the purpose), a single institution or organisation with a formal and full mandate from partners, to represent the National Node

Note: *ad hoc legal entity means a company, an association or another type of organization that has legal rights and responsibilities, including the right to make contracts (for example, Service Level Agreements), to pay E-RIHS ERIC membership fees, and the responsibility to pay debts, established for the purpose of participating in E-RIHS ERIC.*

- A legally binding agreement with provisions that cover the commitment of all institutions or organisations to the ERIC. Name the structure and the type of legal agreement:

Note: *A "legally binding consortium agreement" or any other kind of binding agreement like a Joint Research Unit is a contract between partners that is enforceable under national (and thus European) Law. National Nodes using these options cannot formally have legal personality. This option gives more flexibility in terms of commitment.*

- **NOT APPLICABLE** (choose this option only if the National Node has not been formed yet)

Country of the National Node	Type of the a formal legal agreement	Type of a legally binding agreement	Clarify, please:
Belgium	A legally binding agreement	Memorandum of Understanding	
Cyprus	NOT APPLICABLE		
France	A legally binding agreement	Consortium agreement	
Greece	A legally binding agreement	Memorandum of Understanding	
Hungary	A non-binding agreement		A kind of MoU signed by the directors that we are E-RIHS.hu and working towards E-RIHS. It was prepared before E-RIHS PP but it is still in force. It must be re-worked.
Italy	A legally binding agreement	Joint Research Unit	
Malta	A legally binding agreement	Memorandum of Understanding	
Netherlands	A non-binding agreement		Most parties involved signed a MoU
Poland	A legally binding agreement	Consortium agreement	
Portugal	A legally binding agreement	Memorandum of Understanding	
Romania	A non-binding agreement		In this stage, there is a memorandum of understanding without financial bindings
Slovenia	A legally binding agreement	Consortium agreement	
Spain	A non-binding agreement		A MoU has been signed between institutions. A binding agreement is being considered for the actual committment to the ERIC

UK	A non-binding agreement		The UK National Node is based on a Memorandum of Understanding signed by all partners
B			
Denmark	Single institution/organisation, an ad hoc legal entity.		
Norway	NOT APPLICABLE		
Sweden	NOT APPLICABLE		

France: The FSP acts as the host institution for E-RIHS France. A national "Partnership Agreement" to be signed next June designates the FSP as the corresponding institution to centralise and pay the ERIC membership fees and organise national activities. The Service Level Agreement will be signed for the whole national node by the National coordinator after consultation with the Host institution.

9. Does your National Node have a legal personality?

Note: Legal personality is the ability to sign legal documents as the Node, either through an ad hoc legal entity or with a mandate from all partners

(**NOT APPLICABLE** = choose this option only if the National Node has not been formed yet)

Country of the National Node:	Does your National Node have a legal personality?	If NO: Clarify who the signatory is and how the signing process is handled (e.g. all members sign, or a lead institution can sign on behalf of National Node partners)
Belgium	NO	all members sign
Cyprus	NOT APPLICABLE	
France	NO	The Host Institution is mandated to sign on behalf of all consortium members after an internal validation procedure by the Governing Board.
Greece	NO	FORTH president
Hungary	NO	Besides the initial MoU, nothing had to be signed yet.
Italy	NO	The lead institution of the national node has the mandate to sign and represent the Italian node, as foreseen in the JRJ.
Malta	NO	This is being discussed, but at present lies within the Office of the Permanent Secretary, Ministry for the National Heritage, the Arts and Local Government
Netherlands	NO	At the moment, signing process is constricted to the National Coordinator as staff member of RCE, the hosting entity
Poland	NO	The President (Rector) of the lead institution (Nicolaus Copernicus University) on behalf of NN partners
Portugal	NO	Lead institution can sign on behalf of National Node partners
Romania	NO	It has no legal personality, yet.
Slovenia	NO	Currently, all members are signatories. An Annex to the Consortium Agreement would be

		necessary to enable the lead partner to sign on behalf of all the Members.
Spain	NO	In the current situation, all members need to sign. This might change in the future if a binding agreement is signed.
UK		The UK national node does not yet exist legally. AHRC has received national funding to establish RICHeS (Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science) of which E-RIHS.uk will be a part..
B		
Denmark	NO	Lead institution signs
Norway	NOT APPLICABLE	
Sweden	NOT APPLICABLE	

Hungary: The National Coordinator has mandate to liaise with the National Research, Development and Innovation Office, which oversees ERIC-s.

Malta: The Rector of the University is the signatory for the University of Malta (all entities); there is also a side agreement where all the Departments/Faculties have agreed to participate in E-RIHS.

10. Other comments to Section 2:

Country of the National Node:	10. Other comments to Section 2:
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	The FSP acts as the host institution for E-RIHS France. A national "Partnership Agreement" to be signed next June designates the FSP as the corresponding institution to centralise and pay the ERIC membership fees and organise national activities. The Service Level Agreement will be signed for the whole national node by the National coordinator after consultation with the Host institution.
Greece	
Hungary	"The National Coordinator has mandate to liaise with the National Research, Development and Innovation Office, which oversees ERIC-s.
Italy	
Malta	The Rector of the University is the signatory for the University of Malta (all entities); there is also a side agreement where all the Departments/Faculties have agreed to participate in E-RIHS.
Netherlands	
Poland	
Portugal	
Romania	
Slovenia	No comment.
Spain	
UK	
B	
Denmark	
Norway	
Sweden	

Section 3: Access

11. Does your National Node (or equivalent structure) provide access to facilities (independently to IPERION HS)?

- a) Is such access awarded through a competitive process?
- b) Are the rules for access provision (including the selection process) formalised in a public document?
- c) Is there personnel formally dedicated to access management? (Either through direct employment, secondment, or other formal commitments)
- d) Is there funding formally dedicated to access costs (including operation costs, travel and accommodation for users or MOLAB researchers)?
- e) Does a user pay an access fee (see *Definitions*)?
- f) How many types of services is your National Node offering in 2023:

Country of the National Node:	Does your National Node provide access to facilities	Is such access awarded through a competitive process?	Are the rules for access provision formalised in a public document?	Is there personnel formally dedicated to access management?	Is there funding formally dedicated to access costs	Does a user pay an access fee?	MOLAB	FIXLAB	ARCHLAB	Total	Do you plan to start providing access to facilities (separately from IPERION HS)?	Explain, please:
Belgium	NOT										NOT	As long as the node does not receive any structural funding from the Belgian or regional governments, no sustainable access provision can be guaranteed
Cyprus	YES	NOT	NOT	YES	NOT	YES	6	3	0	9		
France	NOT										YES	
Greece	YES	NOT	NOT	NOT	NOT	NOT	4	2	0	6		
Hungary	YES	NOT	NOT	NOT	NOT	NOT	1	4	1	6		
Italy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NOT	57	13	0	70		
Malta	NOT										YES	
Netherlands	YES	NOT	YES	NOT	NOT	YES	0	0	0	0		
Poland	YES	YES	YES	NOT	NOT	NOT	13	22	0	35		
Portugal	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NOT	12	19	0	31		
Romania	YES	YES	YES	NOT	NOT	NOT	24	30	5	59		

Slovenia	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NOT	15	40	2	57		
Spain	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NOT	2	6	2	10		
UK	NOT										YES	
Total A	10/4	6/4	6/4	6/4	4/6	2/8	134	139	10	283		
Denmark	NOT										YES	
Norway	YES	NOT	NOT	YES	NOT	YES	0	7	0	7		
Sweden	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NOT	5	16	0	14		
Total B	2/1	1/1	1/1	2/0	1/2	1/1	5	7	0	21		
Total A+B	12/5	7/5	7/5	8/4	5/7	3/9	139	155	10	304		

Notice: next tables concern YES only, Nodes not providing access marked with

Sweden: Users do not pay an access fee but they pay travel costs for themselves (FIXLAB) or for the lab staff (MOLAB).

Norway The number 0 for the MOLAB-like and ARCHLAB-like services are not accurate.

Addresses of web-sites with rules for access provision (including the selection process) formalised in a public document:

Country of the National Node:	Provide a link, if available or explain if not, please
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	
Greece	
Hungary	
Italy	https://www.e-rihs.it/en/politica-di-accesso/
Malta	

Netherlands	https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/onderwerpen/laboratoriumonderzoek/onderzoek-en-advies-op-aanvraag/formulier
Poland	http://www.e-rihs.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/regulamin-MOLAB_FIXLAB-PL.pdf (in Polish)"
Portugal	https://www.e-rihs.pt/acessos.php
Romania	
Slovenia	https://www.e-rihs.si/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/E-RIHS.SI-Pravila-dostopa.pdf
Spain	https://www.e-rihs.es/inicio/convocatoria-de-accesos-al-nodo-espanol-de-e-rihs/
UK	
B	
Denmark	
Norway	
Sweden	https://www.raa.se/museer/forskning-och-kunskapsuppbyggnad/kulturarvslaboratoriet/gastkollega-vid-kulturarvslaboratoriet-2/ansok-om-att-bli-gastkollega/

g) h) How many access projects, not counting IPERION HS access, were completed in 2021 and 2022:

Note: Access project: a single project, with a defined beneficiary, may comprise one or more services

Country of the National Node:	Projects completed in 2021	Projects completed in 2022
Belgium		
Cyprus	15	50
France		
Greece	5	4
Hungary	25	30
Italy	11	14
Malta		
Netherlands	168	163
Poland	14	21
Portugal	22	22
Romania	10	10
Slovenia	6	7
Spain	0	0
Sweden	16	17
UK		
Total A	276	321
B		
Denmark		
Norway	8	19
Sweden	16	17
Total B	24	36
Total A+B	300	357

Slovenia: It is an estimation. At the national level we don't divide access service to MOLAB, FIXLAB and ARCHLAB and we are currently developing the Catalogue of Services. It is likely that this will involve about 40-50 services (i.e. access to individual pieces of equipment).

i) What types of institutions are your users typically associated with/employed at? Please provide an approximate distribution (in %):

Country of the National Node:	Public sector	Private sector	Research/academic	Other (e.g. religious)
Belgium				
Cyprus	60	10	10	20
France				
Greece	100	0	0	0
Hungary	70	0	30	0
Italy	32	0	68	0
Malta				
Netherlands	0	0	0	100
Poland	71	0	19	10
Portugal	45	10	45	0
Romania	70	10	10	10
Slovenia	50	0	40	10
Spain	40	0	50	10
Sweden	75	0	20	5
UK				
B				
Denmark				
Norway	13	38	50	0

Spain: The 1st call for access of E-RIHS.es has just been launched, and is still open. Therefore, the type of institutions is just an estimation. Considering the private sector, only non-for-profit institutions are considered.

j) Can you identify and calculate units of access related to the services offered?

Note: unit of access is a common measure of involvement of the provider into a service, usually counted in units of time (days, hours etc.)

YES, NOT, PARTIALLY (for some institutions only)

k) Do you use units of access as a common practice in your Node (e.g., cost model of access)

l) Do you know how to/can you calculate the monetary cost of the access services offered?

m) Is there a cost model for the access services offered?

Country of the National Node:	Can you identify and calculate units of access related to the services offered?	Name it, please:	Do you use units of access as a common practice in your Node (e.g., cost model of access)	Do you know how to/can you calculate the monetary cost of the access services offered?	Is there a cost model for the access services offered?
Belgium					
Cyprus	YES	hours	YES	YES	YES
France					
Greece	YES	days	YES	NO	NO
Hungary	YES	For the same types of access as in Iperion, the same way. For the smaller equipments it is much less clear.	NO	PARTIALLY	NO
Italy	YES	days	YES	YES	PARTIALLY
Malta					
Netherlands	NO		NO	NO	PARTIALLY
Poland	YES	days	YES	NO	NO
Portugal	NO		NO	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY

Romania	NO		NO	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY
Slovenia	YES	access hour	YES	YES	YES
Spain	YES	Days	YES	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY
Sweden	YES	We count each project as one access unit. Each project may run for any length of time from just a few days to several years.	NO	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY
UK					
Total A	7/3		6/3	2/3/5	1/3/6
B					
Denmark					
Norway	YES	hours	NO	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY
Sweden	YES	We count each project as one access unit. Each project may run for any length of time from just a few days to several years.	NO	PARTIALLY	PARTIALLY
Total B	2/0		0/2	0/0/1	0/0/1
Total A+B	9/3		6/5	2/3/6	1/3/7

12. What activities supporting the heritage science community does your National Node provide/participate in (multiple options possible)?

Country of the National Node:	Training	Conferences	Summer schools	Project preparation and implementation	Policy	Joint Research Activities	Public engagement	Grant funding	Other expert	Other
Belgium				x		x				
Cyprus	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
France	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Greece	x		x	x		x	x			
Hungary	x		x	x		x	x			
Italy	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			

Malta											Individual entities within the NN provide access to services and expert support, as well as public engagement, but this is not formalised within the NN. Discussions to do so are under way.
Netherlands		x		x				x	x		
Poland	x	x		x							
Portugal	x	x	x			x	x	x	x		
Romania	x	x	x	x			x				
Slovenia	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			
Spain	x	x		x		x			x		
UK											It is not possible to provide details yet of what activities supporting the heritage science community will the National Node provide or participate in.
Total A	10	9	8	11	3	9	8	5	4	1	
B											
Denmark	x		x			x			x		
Norway	x	x		x			x				
Sweden	x	x		x		x	x				
Total B	3	2	1	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	
Total A+B	13	11	9	13	3	11	10	5	5	2	

13. Other comments to Section 3:

Country of the National Node:	Other comments
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	Several activities will be pooled together with FSP and/or other members' ongoing activities. Access to facilities is already granted through some node members but without a single entry point.
Greece	
Hungary	All participating institutions serve the HS community but there is no "phase transition" in the actual practices yet. We have some dedicated E-RIHS.hu activities such as an E-RIHS.hu meeting but most things are done individually, albeit with the E-RIHS.hu label. (For example, the access provided is not centralised.) For the large scale institutions, there are activities which are somewhat general but still beneficial for the HS community. A "general" carbon dating summer school, for example.
Italy	The training support includes the National Ph.D. program on Heritage Science.
Malta	See note above.
Netherlands	At the moment, the major access is facilitated by our research lab in Amsterdam. Apart from this, we have special E-RIHS projects (about four per year). Access is always free for Dutch users and paid for by international users.
Poland	
Portugal	
Romania	
Slovenia	Comment to 11f: It is an estimation. At the national level we don't divide access service to MOLAB, FIXLAB and ARCHLAB and we are currently developing the Catalogue of Services. It is likely that this will involve about 40-50 services (i.e. access to individual pieces of equipment).

Spain	The 1st call for access of E-RIHS.es has just been launched, and is still open. Therefore, the type of institutions (Question 11.i) is just an estimation. Considering the private sector, only non-for-profit institutions are considered.
UK	
B	
Denmark	
Norway	The number 0 for the MOLAB-like and ARCHLAB-like services are not accurate.
Sweden	11e. Users do not pay an access fee but they pay travel costs for themselves (FIXLAB) or for the lab staff (MOLAB).

Section 4: Budget

Disclaimer:

Although this survey and its questions were very carefully drafted, due to the possible differences between financial methods of the applicants, the result of this survey is mostly indicative and the data can't be compared unconditionally.

14. Estimate the average annual budget of your National Node, in Euro

(including both monetary and in-kind contributions for access, training and any other activities supporting the HS community)?

Note: do not include IPERION HS and ERIHS IP funding. Leave the field empty if an estimation is not possible.

Country of the National Node	Monetary	in-kind
Belgium		
Cyprus		
France	366000	240000
Greece		50000
Hungary		
Italy	1000000	160000
Malta		
Netherlands	400000	150000
Poland	0	5000
Portugal	1000000	100000
Romania	300000	200000
Slovenia	2000000	300000
Spain		
UK		
Total A	5066000	1205000
B		
Denmark		3000
Norway		
Sweden		790000
Total B		793000
Total A+B	5066000	1998000

Slovenia: for in-kind we considered estimated national in-kind contribution for E-RIHS ERIC and it comes from national funding of Slovenian partners. Monetary income as for 2022 and includes equipment grants.

15. Is your National Node currently directly funded?

Note: do not include IPERION HS and ERIHS IP funding, only dedicated and specific funding for National Node activities. Do not include in-kind contribution from partner institutions.

15a. What is the monetary income structure of your National Node (including access, infrastructure upgrade and maintenance, training and any other HS activities linked to E-RIHS) in Euro, in 2022:

Country of the National Node	Is your National Node currently directly funded?	Financial contributions from member/partner institutions:	European Structural Investment Funds	National funding	Regional funding	Access fees from public bodies/organizations	Access fees from private organizations	Private donations or grants	European Commission grants	TOTAL
Belgium	YES	0	0	204000	0	0	0	0	0	204000
Cyprus	NO									0
France	YES	6000	0	360000	0	0	0	0	0	366000
Greece	NO									0
Hungary	NO									0
Italy	YES	0	4200000	1000000	2000000	0	0	0	350000	7550000
Malta	NO									0
Netherlands	NO									0
Poland	YES			10000						10000
Portugal	YES	0	1000000	500000	0	0	0	0	0	1500000
Romania	NO									0
Slovenia	YES	0	36000	3326968	0	0	0	0	466116	3829084
Spain	YES	0	0	25000	0	0	0	0	0	25000
UK	NO									
Total A	6/8	6000	5236000	5415968	2000000	0	0	0	816116	13474084
B										
Denmark	NO									
Norway	NO									
Sweden	YES	0	0	790000	0	0	0	0	0	790000

Total B	1/2	0	0	790000	0	0	0	0	0	790000
Total A+B	7/10	6000	5236000	6205968	2000000	0	0	0	816116	14264084

Poland: 2021 and 2022 only

15b. If your National Node has received European Commission grants such as Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe (excluding IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP funding, also any funding granted directly to Node members) for E-RIHS-related activities or services, please indicate which ones :

Country of the National Node	Joint Research activities for improving services or developing new ones	Training	Research projects that make use of E-RIHS facilities	Public engagement	Recommendations for policy-making or standardisation	Networking and synergies with other European initiatives	Other	NON-APPLICABLE	TOTAL
Belgium								x	1
Cyprus									
France								x	1
Greece									
Hungary									
Italy	x		x		x				3
Malta									
Netherlands									
Poland									
Portugal		x	x			x			3
Romania									

Slovenia	x	x	x		x	x			5
Spain					x	x			2
UK									
Total A	2	2	3	0	3	3	0	2	15
B									
Denmark									
Norway									
Sweden								x	1
Total B								1	
Total A+B	2	2	3	0	3	3	0	3	16

15c. Do you have a 5-year budget plan?

Country of the National Node	Do you have a 5-year budget plan?
Belgium	NO
Cyprus	
France	NO
Greece	
Hungary	
Italy	YES
Malta	
Netherlands	
Poland	
Portugal	NO
Romania	
Slovenia	YES
Spain	NO
UK	
Total A	2/4
B	
Denmark	
Norway	
Sweden	NO
Total B	0/1
Total A+B	2/5

15d. Do you have shared accounting practices or guidelines?

Country of the National Node	Do you have shared accounting practices or guidelines?					
	YES			NO		
	Based on actual costs	Based on a fair market value approach	Based on established standard costs	We plan to adopt common rules for cost estimation	We do not plan to adopt common rules for cost estimation	It depends on future ERIC requirements
Belgium						x
Cyprus						
France				x		
Greece						
Hungary						
Italy	x					
Malta						
Netherlands						
Poland						
Portugal	x					
Romania						
Slovenia			x			
Spain	x					
Sweden						x
UK						
Total A	3	0	1	1	0	1
B						
Denmark						
Norway						
Sweden						x
Total B						1
Total A+B	3	0	1	1	0	2

16. Do you anticipate your National Node to receive funding in 2024?

Country of the National Node	Do you anticipate your National Node to receive funding in 2024?
Belgium	DON'T KNOW
Cyprus	YES

France	YES
Greece	YES
Hungary	DON'T KNOW
Italy	YES
Malta	DON'T KNOW
Netherlands	YES
Poland	DON'T KNOW
Portugal	YES
Romania	DON'T KNOW
Slovenia	YES
Spain	YES
UK	DON'T KNOW
Total A	8/0/6
B	
Denmark	NO
Norway	NO
Sweden	YES
Total B	1/2/0
Total A+B	9/2/6

17. Is your National Node subjected to mandatory reporting (e.g., related to the National Roadmap updating) or national audits?

Country of the National Node	Do you anticipate your National Node to receive funding in 2024?
Belgium	NO
Cyprus	PARTIALLY
France	YES
Greece	NO
Hungary	PARTIALLY
Italy	YES
Malta	PARTIALLY
Netherlands	PARTIALLY
Poland	YES
Portugal	YES
Romania	YES
Slovenia	YES
Spain	PARTIALLY
UK	NO
Total A	6/3/5
B	
Denmark	PARTIALLY
Norway	NO
Sweden	YES
Total B	1/1/1
Total A+B	7/4/6

18. What is the annual cost structure of the National Node (in Euro)?

- 18a. Employed personnel (cost of staff, including only personnel employed specifically for National Node services) by amount: EURO.
- 18b. Employed personnel (cost of staff, including only personnel employed specifically for National Node services) by full-time equivalent: PM
Note: Full-time equivalent (counted in personal months – PM): to calculate, divide the total amount (as for p. 18a) by 12 x the average monthly full-time salary of the person employed in a similar position
- 18c. In-Kind Human Resources (cost of staff, including personnel employed at partner institutions and providing services instead of monetary contributions) by amount EURO
- 18d. In-Kind Human Resources (cost of staff, including personnel employed at partner institutions and providing services in lieu of monetary contributions) by full time equivalent: PM
- 18e. Consumables, training, travel and other costs EURO
- 18f. Investments into infrastructure and equipment, including servicing EURO

Country of the National Node	Employed personnel by amount:	Employed personnel by full-time equivalent	In-Kind Human Resources by amount	In-Kind Human Resources by full time equivalent:	Consumables, training, travel and other costs	Investments into infrastructure and equipment, including servicing	Total by amount	Total by PM
Belgium	0	0.0	3250	6.0	0	0	3250	6.0
Cyprus	20000	6.0	30000	6.0	5000	50000	105000	12.0
France	20000	4.0	190000	48.0	50000	360000	620000	52.0
Greece	0	0.0	40000	12.0	10000	15000	65000	12.0
Hungary	12000	6.0	38000	19.0	60000	80000	190000	25.0
Italy	160000	40.0	160000	40.0	1100000	1800000	3220000	80.0
Malta	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0
Netherlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0
Poland	0	0.0	5000	2.5	0	0	5000	2.5
Portugal	120000	5.0	0	0.0	0	500	120500	5.0
Romania	250	28	100	12	20	100	470	40.0
Slovenia	37971	10.0	300614	77.0	367902	1222886	1929373	87.0
Spain	39200	10.5	33200	7.3	21600	0	94000	17.8
UK	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0
Total A	409421	109,5	800164	229,8	1614522	3528486	6352593	339,3
B								
Denmark	20000	5	0	0	0	1000000	1002000	5
Norway	792589	88.7	233219	26.1	107865	890887	2024560	114.8
Sweden	600000	90.0	0	0.0	160000	30000	790000	90.0
Total B	1412589	183,7	233219	26,1	267865	1920887	3834560	209,8
Total A+B	1822010	293	1033383	256	1882387	5449373	10187153	549,1

France: Question 18 refers to the estimated stable state of the budget once accesses and the ERIC are started.

Slovenia: Comment for points 18c and 18d: at the level of the national node, we report “National Own contribution” and not “in-kind” as requested here. Namely, such funding comes from the national funding of Slovenian partners. Only from the E-RIHS ERIC perspective we can consider this as the possible in-kind contribution of Slovenian National Node to ERIC.

Comment for 18f: servicing is reported under consumables and we cannot calculate it as a separate budget item.

General comment: For point 18. we considered year 2023

Spain: Current monetary income comes only from a CSIC grant awarded through an internal competitive call, which covers only CSIC expenses and general services for the node (for instance, preparation of the first call for access). Estimation of annual costs (question 18) is based in the situation of the node for year 2023. Costs and revenue (mainly in-kind) is expected to be significantly higher with the ERIC running.

At this moment, as we don't have a future upgrade plan, we cannot provide even an estimate of the upgrades in next 5 years.

Denmark: corrected by PT after M. Collins e-mail, data for 2022

19. Do you have a separate service and maintenance budget?

Country of the National Node	Do you have a separate service and maintenance budget?
Belgium	NO
Cyprus	NO
France	NO
Greece	NO
Hungary	NO
Italy	NO
Malta	NO
Netherlands	NO
Poland	NO
Portugal	NO
Romania	NO
Slovenia	YES
Spain	NO
UK	NO
Total A	1/13
B	
Denmark	NO
Norway	NO
Sweden	NO
Total B	0/3
Total A+B	1/16

20. Provide an estimate of funding for future infrastructure/instrumentation upgrades in the 5-year perspective? (Please enter the estimated numerical value in €)

Country of the National Node	Public funding	Private funding/donors
Belgium	0	0
Cyprus	50000	500000
France	360000	0
Greece	100000	0
Hungary	400000	0
Italy	1000000	1000000
Malta	0	0
Netherlands	3000000	0
Poland	200000	0
Portugal	2000000	0
Romania	450	
Slovenia	8757217	0
Spain	0	0
UK	0	0
Total A	15867667	1500000
B		
Denmark	0	0
Norway	8956706	0
Sweden	500000	0
Total B	9456706	0
Total A+B	25324373	1500000

France: Question 20a includes a part of the EquipEx ESPADON funding related to E-RIHS until 2029 (ANR-21-ESRE-0050)

Denmark: We have received funding to establish E-RIHS.dk. We are hoping to develop an income stream

Norway: The infrastructure has not been established yet and the information is based on the old application without considering the inflation.. A cost of about 102 414 000 NOK was estimated for a 5-year plan in the old application.

21. Do you have a 5-year infrastructure/instrumentation upgrade plan?

Country of the National Node	Do you have a 5-year infrastructure/instrumentation upgrade plan?
Belgium	NO
Cyprus	YES
France	NO
Greece	NO
Hungary	NO
Italy	NO

Malta	NO
Netherlands	NO
Poland	NO
Portugal	NO
Romania	NO
Slovenia	YES
Spain	NO
UK	NO
Total A	2/12
B	
Denmark	NO
Norway	YES
Sweden	YES
Total B	2/1
Total A+B	4/13

Spain: At this moment, as we don't have a future upgrade plan, we can not provide even an estimate of the upgrades in next 5 years.

22. Other comments to Section 4:

Country of the National Node	
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	Question 18 refers to the estimated stable state of the budget once accesses and the ERIC are started. Question 20a includes a part of the EquipEx ESPADON funding related to E-RIHS until 2029 (ANR-21-ESRE-0050)
Greece	
Hungary	The budget questions are hard. Costs are not separated. None of us is just dedicated to E-RIHS. What is stated explicitly, for example, that ATOMKI plans 4 FTE in heritage science for 2024. But this work is, mostly, providing access and do the research together with the Users, and in the justification towards our financing body we refer to E-RIHS, on both national and international level. But I do not, how much it will be "real" E-RIHS activity. Something similar, for the Research Centre for Energy Research.
Italy	
Malta	Estimates cannot be provided in this section as the National Node has only recently been set up and the modus operandi is under discussion
Netherlands	The funding and costs are simply too diverse and volatile to be more precise. There is also a distinction between the lab and the node. We are not interested in the various labs, but look at the questions and act accordingly.
Poland	
Portugal	
Slovenia	Comment for point 14: for in-kind we considered estimated national in-kind contribution for E-RIHS ERIC and it comes from national funding of Slovenian partners. Comment for points 18c and 18d: at the level of the national node, we report

	<p>“National Own contribution” and not “in-kind” as requested here. Namely, such funding comes from the national funding of Slovenian partners. Only from the E-RIHS ERIC perspective we can consider this as the possible in-kind contribution of Slovenian National Node to ERIC.</p> <p>Comment for 18f: servicing is reported under consumables and we cannot calculate it as a separate budget item.</p> <p>General comment: For point 18. we considered year 2023</p>
Spain	<p>Current monetary income comes only from a CSIC grant awarded through an internal competitive call, which covers only CSIC expenses and general services for the node (for instance, preparation of the first call for access). Estimation of annual costs (question 18) is based in the situation of the node for year 2023. Costs and revenue (mainly in-kind) is expected to be significantly higher with the ERIC running.</p> <p>At this moment, as we don't have a future upgrade plan, we can not provide even an estimate of the upgrades in next 5 years.</p>
UK	
B	
Denmark	We have received funding to establish E-RIHS.dk. We are hoping to develop an income stream
Norway	The infrastructure has not been established yet and the information is based on the old application without considering the inflation.. A cost of about 102414000 NOK was estimated for a 5-year plan in the old application.
Sweden	The answers refer to one institution only - the heritage laboratory of the Swedish National Heritage Board. It is a national resource for heritage science that is entirely funded with public money. A wider national node does not yet exist.

Section 5: Future plans

23. Please provide a rough and not binding estimation of the number of services the National Node will propose for inclusion in the Catalogue of Services of ERIHS ERIC:

Note: services refer to procedures/techniques/methods/archives, analogous to the items listed in the IPERION HS Transnational Access offer: MOLAB-like: service provided at User's location, FIXLAB-like: service provided at Provider's facility (laboratory), ARCHLAB-like: access to the Providers' archives (enter zeros if the National Node has not been formed yet)

Country of the National Node	ARCHLAB	FIXLAB	MOLAB	Total
Belgium	2	0	0	2
Cyprus	0	2	5	7
France	3	15	8	26
Greece	0	5	10	15
Hungary	1	4	0	5
Italy	0	15	60	75
Malta	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	0	0	0	0
Poland	0	10	5	15
Portugal	2	20	15	37
Romania	5	30	24	59
Slovenia	3	20	10	33
Spain	3	6	4	13
UK	0	0	0	0
Total A	19	127	141	287
B				
Denmark	0	0	0	0
Norway	0	9	2	11
Sweden	0	0	0	0
Total B	0	9	2	11
Total A+B	19	136	143	298

Slovenia: We plan on proposing several advanced labs that gather more pieces of equipment (that could be construed as "services") integrated with expertise. It would be very good to define what service is (access to 1 piece of equipment or several pieces of equipment along with the relevant expertise...). The proposed Slovenian offer would include:

- Heritage Macromolecular lab (already recognised within IPERION HS, and offering different types of chromatography, FTIR micro-imaging, FT and dispersive Raman microscopy, IFM)
- Laboratory for advanced surface analysis (XPS, ToF-SIMS, DESI ToF)
- Laboratory for heritage wood
- Preventive conservation and olfactory heritage lab
- Laboratory for built heritage

24. Are you planning or already offering access to a National DIGILAB?

Note: DIGILAB refers to “digital knowledge and data repositories, collaborative tools, and online research facilities” exploitable by the Heritage Science community. National DIGILAB refers to such resources directly organised or co-organised by your National Node.

Country of the National Node		
Belgium	YES	An ongoing project funded by the Belgian federal science policy, HESCIDA, aims to create the first of its kind federated repository for DIGILAB.
Cyprus	YES	EPHEMERA - an online platform for scientific visualisation of 3D models of monuments, sites and artefacts
France	YES	Tools and services are developed within ESPADON, N-DAME, and other internal activities of Node Members. They will be open and/or promoted through E-RIHS France.
Greece	NO	
Hungary	NO	
Italy	NO	
Malta	YES	We cannot give an estimate as the NN is in its early discussions. We are also discussing providing expert advice and training in the areas where we have expertise
Netherlands	YES	There are plans for extra datamining and the gathering of extra information
Poland	YES	Preventive conservation platform HERIe
Portugal	NO	
Romania	YES	Data processing, Data management, Preventive Conservation Instruments etc.
Slovenia	YES	We are working on building DIGILAB at the national level
Spain	NO	
UK		
Total A	7/6	
B		
Denmark	NO	
Norway	NO	

Sweden	YES	SweDigArch infrastructure http://swedigarch.se/
Total B	1/2	
Total A+B	8/8	

25. Are you following established rules (referring to FAIR principles, open Data) for the Data produced in Access projects, as part of a Data Management Policies / Data repositories framework at **National level**?

Country of the National Node	
Belgium	YES
Cyprus	YES
France	YES
Greece	NO
Hungary	DON'T KNOW
Italy	YES
Malta	DON'T KNOW
Netherlands	YES
Poland	DON'T KNOW
Portugal	YES
Romania	YES
Slovenia	YES
Spain	YES
UK	YES
Total A	10/1/3
B	
Denmark	YES
Norway	DON'T KNOW
Sweden	YES
Total B	2/0/1
Total A+B	12/1/4

26. Has your country already committed or has plans to commit to participation in the E-RIHS ERIC?

Country of the National Node	
Belgium	YES
Cyprus	YES
France	YES
Greece	YES
Hungary	YES
Italy	YES
Malta	YES
Netherlands	YES
Poland	YES
Portugal	NO
Romania	YES
Slovenia	YES

Spain	YES
UK	YES
Total A	13/1
B	
Denmark	NO
Norway	NO
Sweden	YES
Total B	1/2
Total A+B	14/3

27. Are the scientific or professional representatives of your country willing to join the Enlargement Board?

Note: the Enlargement Board (EB) is made up of scientists representing Countries that are either not yet engaged in E-RIHS or are engaged in E-RIHS, without supporting the establishment of the ERIC yet. The EB will be engaged during the project ERIHS-IP lifetime to boost interest in E-RIHS, and it will be provided with information and documents necessary to start the national process to join E-RIHS ERIC.

Denmark	matthew@palaeome.org
Sweden	Jon Yngve Hardeberg, jon.hardeberg@ntnu.no from NTNU-Gjøvik Hana Lukesova, Hana.Lukesova@uib.no

28. Other comments to Section 5:

Country of the National Node	
Belgium	
Cyprus	
France	The number of services includes Node-only services and services opened to E-RIHS Europe.
Greece	
Hungary	As for the FAIR principles, we are working on it,
Italy	
Malta	The National Node has only recently been set up and the modus operandi is under discussion
Netherlands	
Poland	
Portugal	
Romania	
Slovenia	Comment for point 23: We plan on proposing several advanced labs that gather more pieces of equipment (that could be construed as “services”) integrated with expertise. It would be very good to define what service is (access to 1 piece of equipment or several pieces of equipment along with the relevant expertise...). The proposed Slovenian offer would include:

	<p>a) Heritage Macromolecular lab (already recognised within IPERION HS, and offering different types of chromatography, FTIR micro-imaging, FT and dispersive Raman microscopy, IFM)</p> <p>b) Laboratory for advanced surface analysis (XPS, ToF-SIMS, DESI ToF)</p> <p>c) Laboratory for heritage wood</p> <p>d) Preventive conservation and olfactory heritage lab</p> <p>e) Laboratory for built heritage</p>
Spain	Spain has committed to E-RIHS ERIC as founding member
Sweden	
UK	
B	
Denmark	
Norway	We will be bale to commit once the national network will be formally established

Other comments the survey as a whole:

Country of the National Node	
Belgium	
Cyprus	The numbers above are rough estimates and express solely the opinion of the person who filled the questionnaire. Data filled is to be used only internally within the IPERION HS project as indicative and not for any scientific purpose, policy advise, deliverable or any other publication, without prior formal consent by its author.
France	This survey was completed using 2022 numbers when required (including costs); other questions were answered using projections from 2024 to 2028 (access services, DIGILAB, and capital investment).
Greece	
Hungary	Because, at least not yet, there is no specific calls for established nodes of ERIC-s, all money is coming from the general budget of the institutions, apart from the membership fees. In addition, several equipment pieces are also used for other purposes. People are working in other fields, too, although now there are more or less dedicated HS teams at ATOMKI and the Centre for Energy Research. At the moment, it is very hard to pinpoint what is done as "the node" and how much it costs.
Italy	
Malta	We are actively participating in the iCNN meetings and we also meet regularly (ca bimonthly) as a NN. These meetings are helping us develop our "offer" both to E-RIHS and to the local communities through the NN. As part of the local "offer", Malta is developing a National Research Agenda for Cultural Heritage, spearheaded by the Ministry for the National Heritage, the Arts and Local Government, and the Superintendence for Cultural Heritage.
Netherlands	
Poland	
Portugal	
Romania	
Slovenia	
Spain	
UK	
B	
Denmark	

Norway	Unfortunately many information are not currently available and it is not possible to gather them in this short time. Especially concerning the MOLAB-like and ARCHLAB-like services.
Sweden	

Appendix 1: Complete list of institutions forming a National Node

(if established)

The leading institution is shown in bold

Country	The leading institution (is in BOLD) plus Other institutions of your Node, one per line: national language / English
Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium / Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage • Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis / Royal Museums for Art and History • Koninklijke Bibliotheek / Royal Library of Belgium
Cyprus	
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine - Foundation for Heritage Science • Ministère de la Culture (MC) - Ministry of Culture • Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) - National Center for Scientific Research • CY Cergy Paris Université - CY Cergy Paris University • Université Paris-Saclay - Paris-Saclay University • Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN) - National Museum of Natural History <p>These are the members of the Governing Board. Access providers are part of the Node through their parent authorities above.</p> <p>To this day, the list of providers includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France (C2RMF) - Center for Research and Restoration of Museums of France - Laboratoire de Recherche des Monuments Historiques (LRMH) - Research Laboratory for Historical Monuments - Centre d'Élaboration de Matériaux et d'Études Structurales (CEMES) - Center for the Elaboration of Materials and Structural Studies - Institut de Chimie et de Biologie des Membranes et des Nano-objets (CBMN) - Institute of Chemistry and Biology of Membranes and Nano-Objects - Centre interdisciplinaire de conservation et de restauration du patrimoine (CIRCP) - Interdisciplinary Center for Conservation and Restoration of Heritage - Modèles et simulations pour l'architecture et le Patrimoine (MAP) - Models and Simulations for Architecture and Heritage - Centre de recherche sur la conservation des collections (CRC) - Center for Research on Conservation of Collections - Institut d'analyse non-destructive européen des matériaux anciens (IPANEMA) - European Institute for Non Destructive analysis of Ancient Materials - Systèmes et Applications des Technologies de l'Information et de l'Energie (SATIE) - Systems and Applications of Information Technologies and Energy - Equipes de Traitement de l'Information et Systèmes (ETIS) - Teams for Information Treatment and Systems
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITE / FORTH

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ΙΔΡΥΜΑ ΟΡΜΥΛΙΑ / ORMYLIA FOUNDATION ART DIAGNOSIS CENTER
Hungary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atommagkutató Intézet / Institute for Nuclear Research (Debrecen) • Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont / Centre for Energy Research (Budapest) • Wigner Fizikai Kutatóközpont / Wigner Research Centre for Physics (Budapest) • Magyar Nemzeti Múzeum / Hungarian National Museum (Budapest)
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Research Council • Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare / National Institute of Nuclear Physics • Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile / Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
Malta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universita' ta' Malta/University of Malta • Office of the Permanent Secretary, Ministry for the National Heritage, the Arts and Local Government • Superintendence of Cultural Heritage • Heritage Malta • Restoration Directorate • Malta Libraries • National Archives • The Archdiocese of Malta • St John's Co Cathedral Foundation
Netherlands	
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika w Toruniu / Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń • Akademia Górniczo-Hutnicza w Krakowie / AGH University of Science and Technology in Kraków • Akademia Sztuk Pięknych w Krakowie / Academy of Fine Arts in Kraków • Instytut Chemii i Techniki Jądrowej / Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology • Instytut Katalizy i Fizykochemii Powierzchni im. Jerzego Habera PAN / Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry of Polish Academy of Sciences • Instytut Maszyn Przepływowych im. R. Szwalskiego PAN / The Szwalski Institute of Fluid-Flow Machinery of Polish Academy of Science • Muzeum Narodowe w Krakowie / National Museum in Kraków • Narodowe Centrum Badań Jądrowych / National Centre for Nuclear Research • Politechnika Warszawska / Warsaw University of Technology • Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny w Krakowie / Cracow University of Economics • Uniwersytet Jagielloński / Jagiellonian University in Kraków • Uniwersytet Warszawski / University of Warsaw • Uniwersytet Wrocławski / University of Wrocław
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratório HERCULES - Universidade de Évora / HERCULES Laboratory - Evora University • Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil / National Laboratory of Civil Engineering • Laboratório Jose de Figueiredo - Direção Geral de Património Cultural / Jose de Figueiredo Laboratory - General Directorate for Cultural Heritage
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics INOE 2000 • Institutul Național al Patrimoniului/ National Heritage Institute • Institutul de Fizică și Inginerie Nucleară "Horia Hulubei" / "Horia Hulubei" National Institute for R&D in Physics and Nuclear Engineering

Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine Slovenije / Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia • Univerza v Ljubljani / University of Ljubljana • Univerza v Mariboru / University of Maribor • Univerza na Primorskem / University of Primorska • Zavod za gradbeništvo Slovenije / Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute • Kemijski inštitut / National Institute of Chemistry • Inštitut Jožef Stefan / Jožef Stefan Institute • Narodna in Univerzitetna knjižnica / National and University Library
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas / Spanish National Research Council • Centro de Conservación y Restauración de Bienes Culturales de Castilla y León / Center for Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Property of Castilla y León • Centro Nacional de Aceleradores / National Accelerator Center • Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana / National Center for Research on Human Evolution • Universidad del País Vasco-Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Ikerkuntza eta Berrikuntza • Analitikoa - Grupo Investigación e Innovación Analítica / University of the Basque Country, Research and Innovation in Analytical Chemistry Group. • Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España / Spanish Cultural Heritage Institute • Universidad de Barcelona. Sección de Química Analítica del Departamento de Ingeniería • Química y Química Analítica / University of Barcelona. Analytical Chemistry Section of the Department of Chemical Engineering and Analytical Chemistry • Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Servicio de Conservación, Restauración y Estudios Científicos del Patrimonio Arqueológico / Autonomous University of Madrid. Service of Conservation, Restoration and Scientific Studies of Archaeological Heritage
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UCL • British Library • British Museum • Cardiff University • The Courtauld Institute of Art • Diamond • English Heritage • Historic England • Historic Environment Scotland • ISIS • The National Gallery • Nottingham Trent University • Tate • University of Bradford • University of the Arts London • University of Brighton • University of Strathclyde • University of Glasgow • V&A

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University of York"
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The University of Copenhagen • Aarhus University • The Royal School of Conservation • Glyptoteket
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UiO-KHM: Universitetet i Oslo- Kulturhistorisk museum /University of Oslo-Museum of Cultural History • UiO-IAKH: Universitetet i Oslo- Institutt for arkeologi, konservering og historie/University of Oslo- Department of Archaeology, Conservation and History) • UiS: Arkeologisk museum (Universitetet i Stavanger)/Archaeological Museum (University of Stavanger) • UiB: Universitetsmuseet i Bergen (Universitetet i Bergen)/University Museum (University of Bergen) • NTNU: Vitenskapsmuseet (Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet)/Vitenskapmuseum (Norwegian University of Science and Technology- University Museum) • NTNU: Colorlab (Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet i Gjøvik)/Colorlab (Norwegian University of Science and Technology-headquarter in Gjøvik) • UiT: Norges Arktiske Universitetsmuseum (Norges arktiske universitet)/University Museum (The Arctic University of Norway).
Sweden	